

Design and Fault Analysis of Solar Photovoltaic Cable Array Grid Connected Systems

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Abstract: The design and fault analysis of solar photovoltaic (PV) cable array grid-connected systems are crucial aspects in ensuring the reliability, efficiency, and safety of solar power installations. This paper explores the design considerations of PV cable arrays, including selection of cables, connection schemes, and integration with grid systems. Additionally, it addresses fault analysis techniques, focusing on identifying, diagnosing, and mitigating faults that can arise in these systems, such as cable degradation, insulation failures, and environmental factors. A thorough analysis of fault detection methods, including protection mechanisms, is provided. This work aims to optimize the performance and longevity of solar PV systems, ensuring stable and continuous power generation in grid-connected applications.

Keywords: PV, Fault, Line, Ground, Simulink, Array, Power, Grid.

I. INTRODUCTION

The global demand for renewable energy is growing rapidly, with solar energy being one of the most promising sources due to its sustainability, environmental benefits, and decreasing costs of photovoltaic (PV) technologies. A grid-connected solar photovoltaic system comprises various components, such as solar panels, inverters, cables, and connection arrays, working together to harness solar energy and feed it into the electrical grid. The cables in a PV system play a critical role in connecting the solar panels to the inverter and ultimately to the grid, ensuring efficient energy transmission and minimizing losses.

The design of a solar PV cable array involves several considerations, such as the selection of appropriate cable types, their size, and the configuration of the array to ensure optimal performance. It is essential to consider factors like the electrical load, environmental conditions, and mechanical stresses to ensure the system can endure over its expected lifespan. Furthermore, the cabling infrastructure must be designed to minimize energy loss and prevent failures that could disrupt power generation. The proper installation of cables and connectors is crucial, as improper designs can lead to overheating, fire hazards, or loss of system efficiency.

However, designing a robust PV cable system is only part of the equation. Fault analysis is a critical aspect of maintaining the health and efficiency of solar PV systems. Faults in the cable array can occur due to various reasons, including environmental factors such as temperature extremes, humidity, and physical damage during installation. Additionally, long-term issues such as cable degradation and insulation failures can significantly affect the system's performance and safety. Early detection and diagnosis of these faults are crucial to prevent damage, reduce downtime, and ensure that the system operates optimally.

Modern fault detection techniques and protection systems have become increasingly advanced, integrating sensors, monitoring equipment, and predictive maintenance strategies. These methods enable operators to identify faults in real time, accurately pinpoint their locations, and take corrective actions

swiftly. This paper explores different fault types in solar PV cable arrays, including open-circuit faults, short circuits, ground faults, and cable degradation. It also highlights various fault analysis methods such as thermal imaging, visual inspection, and electrical testing.

This introduction provides an overview of the significance of designing robust PV cable systems and the importance of fault analysis in enhancing the performance and longevity of grid-connected solar photovoltaic systems. By addressing both the design and fault analysis aspects, this paper aims to contribute to the improvement of solar PV systems' reliability, safety, and efficiency, ensuring sustainable energy production in line with global renewable energy goals.

II. PROPOSED MODEL

The main objective is to design and fault analysis of solar photovoltaic cable array grid connected systems. Previously it analysis for single PV cable, but in some application there is need to use PV cable array. Therefore proposed model have PV cable array and fault analysis perform with accuracy.

Figure 1: Proposed Model

Figure 1 shows proposed model of fault analysis of dc microgrid with PV cable. In this model, there are sub modules like three phase grid, DC-DC converter, pulse width modulation, Solar panel and MPPT.

Following sub module are used to design proposed model. Each module is connected as per flow block diagram.

- Three phase grid
- DC-DC converter and DC-AC converted
- pulse width modulation(PWM)
- Solar panel
- MPPT Technique

Standard Solar, Inc. as of late finished one of the principal solar microgrid systems with a gridinteractive battery bank in the nation. Being an originally was a test it took a very long time of devotion, inventive building and coordination with key accomplices, utilities and government workplaces to make this venture a reality. The primary portion of this paper will set the phase by clarifying how the microgrid is arrangement, its usefulness and what makes it uncommon. At that point I will investigate the stuff to plan and introduce a solar microgrid system, the exercises gained from this groundbreaking undertaking and what specialized contemplations ought to be made when actualizing this new innovation.

Maximum power point tracking (MPPT) is a calculation actualized in photovoltaic (PV) inverters to constantly modify the impedance seen by the solar cluster to keep the PV system working at, or near, the pinnacle power purpose of the PV panel under fluctuating conditions, such as changing solar irradiance, temperature, and burden. Architects creating solar inverters execute MPPT calculations to expand the power produced by PV systems. The calculations control the voltage to guarantee that the system works at "greatest power point" (or pinnacle voltage) on the power voltage bend, as demonstrated as follows. MPPT calculations are commonly utilized in the controller plans for PV systems. The calculations account for factors, for example, factor irradiance (daylight) and temperature to guarantee that the PV system produces most extreme power consistently. Most extreme power point tracking is a technique utilized normally with wind turbines and photovoltaic (PV) solar systems to boost power extraction under all conditions.

An electrical grid is an interconnected system for conveying power from makers to buyers. It comprises of creating stations that produce electrical power, high voltage transmission lines that convey power from far off sources to demand focuses, and circulation lines that interface singular clients. An AC-AC converter with around sinusoidal info currents and bidirectional power flow can be acknowledged by coupling a heartbeat width modulation (PWM) rectifier and a PWM inverter to the DC-interface. The DC-connect amount is then intrigued by an energy stockpiling component that is regular to the two phases, which is a capacitor C for the voltage DC-interface or an inductor L for the current DC-connect. The PWM rectifier is controlled such that a sinusoidal AC line current is drawn,

which is in phase or hostile to phase (for energy feedback) with the relating AC line phase voltage.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

The proposed model is implemented with MATLAB simulink.

Figure 2: Solar panel

Figure 2 shows solar arrays, it begin with a single solar energy cell known as a photovoltaic cell. “Photo” essentially means light, and “voltaic” refers to voltage, which is a unit of potential electrical energy. When

Figure 3: Voltage vs Power graph

Figure 3 shows voltage vs power graph of solar panel PV-characteristics. X axis show the MPPT value of voltage i.e approx 32 while y axis shows the power i.e. 240W approx.

Figure 4: Voltage vs Current graph

Figure 4 presents voltage vs current graph of solar panel PV-characteristics. X axis show the value of voltage i.e approx 32 while y axis shows the power i.e. 7.5A approx.

Figure 5: Voltage of DC-DC Converter

Figure 5 is showing voltage of DC-DC converter, it achieves 402.8 voltages. In previous model IGBT is used but in proposed model MOSFET is used instead of IGBT.

Figure 6: Load and AC Grid

Figure 6 presents the load element and AC grid. Here 2 phase power line is converted into 3 phase power line by using bridge converter and rectifier.

Figure 7: Load Voltage

Figure 7 is showing output of load. Here 380V is achieved at the output side in this model. So this voltage can be used for any industrial or domestic application.

1. Line-to-Line fault

Figure 8: Line-to-Line fault

Figure 8 is showing line-to-line fault condition. In which line have fault while ground have no fault. A line to line fault is one where short circuiting occurs between two phases of a system.

Figure 9: PV line voltage and current graph-2

Figure 9 is showing line-to-line fault voltage and current. The value of voltage is 12V and current is 0A.

2. Line to ground fault

Figure 10: Line to ground fault

Figure 10 is showing line-to-ground Fault. Generally, a single line-to-ground fault on a transmission line occurs when one conductor drops to the ground in which line have fault while ground have no fault.

Figure 11: PV line voltage and current-3

Figure 11 is showing line-to-ground fault voltage and current. The value of voltage is 0V and current is 80A.

Table 1: Simulation Result

Sr No.	Fault condition	Voltage (V)	Current (A)
1	No fault	202	80
2	Line to Line	12	0
3	Line to Ground	0	80
4	Combined Fault	0	0

Table 2: Result comparison

Sr No.	Parameter	Previous Model	Proposed Model
1	Switch	IGBT	MOSFET
2	Output	DC Microgrid	DC & AC microgrid
3	Fault	All case	All case
4	Load output voltage	Not Mention	380V
5	DC-DC converter Output Voltage	380 V	402.8 V
6	Software	PSCAD/EMTDC	MATLAB

Table 1 shows simulation results and table 2 showing comparison of proposed model analysis results with previous model results. Therefore above result shows, proposed model give significant improved analysis rather than the existing model.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the simulation, it was determined that the suggested study activity would comprise fault analysis of the presented model design. The utilization of a larger number of photovoltaic cables or arrays of cables is indicative of their deployment in wide areas. A model that has been proposed illustrates the usefulness of photovoltaic (PV) electricity in both industrial and residential settings. Given this, it is abundantly evident that the suggested model and analysis is far superior to the one that is now in use.

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